

Constraint-Based Protocols for Distributed Problem Solving

(extended abstract)

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DISTRIBUTED PROBLEM SOLVING (DPS) decomposes problems into subproblems to be solved by interacting, cooperative software agents. Thus, DPS is suitable for modeling the solving of problems characterized by many interdependencies among subproblems, both in the context of parallel and distributed architectures.

Concurrent Constraint Programming (CCP) is a powerful framework to support DPS, since it provides a direct implementation of the notion of shared, reusable, incrementally refined information, where constraints can declaratively implement both local problem solving as well as exchange of information, and hence DPS, among agents. To optimally solve DPS problems with CCP we need however capabilities for tuning the protocol for constraint communication at the execution level, according to such factors as the specific instance of the DPS problem and the characteristics of the underlying system architecture.

In our research we introduce two general protocols for DPS, the *Request-Subrequest Protocol* and the *Local Caching Protocol* which are based on the hypothesis of *minimal* and *maximal* reuse respectively. In the first approach all information is made potentially available, but it can be delivered only in response to specific requests, while in the second approach all information is immediately broadcast to all agents, with a reduced amount of network traffic (as the complications of the request-based protocol are avoided), but with more risk of cluttering agents with useless information.

Therefore, the notion of *quantity of reuse* R of information has been formally introduced, to obtain a heuristic providing a criterion of choice between the protocols, to figure out whether the protocol with minimal or maximal reuse, or even a hybrid approach, is appropriate. High values of R suggest to choose the local caching protocol, while low values of R make the request-subrequest protocol more convenient.

Obviously, the two protocols are at the very opposite ends of a spectrum of possible protocols and intermediate cases are possible, for instance, when automatic deliveries are done for subsets of agents. For many practical applications these cases seem to be the most useful, so we need techniques for assigning agents to appropriate “interest groups”, and to allow flexible tuning of group-based communication. Furthermore, we shall observe by simple, but generalizable examples that the optimal solution of a DPS problem may involve splitting the problem into subproblems which are optimally solved according to different protocols. Again, we need flexible ways for expressing such protocols, and for mixing them freely in the overall solution of a particular problem. Besides, we need ways of guessing the right protocol, or the right *melange* of protocols, for specific problems. This calls for contributions from such diverse fields as programming linguistics, learning and simulation.

Another approach for gaining further insight on the issue of reuse of information comes from formal language theory, assuming that we could encode a number of DPS problems as context-free grammars (just as Definite Clause Grammars have been shown to provide a general framework for logic programming). Under this assumption, one could study the reuse of information from the point of view of asymptotical combinatorial analysis for context-free grammars. This would involve the use of Schützenberger’s techniques based on algebraic and generating functions. These techniques allow the analytical computation of combinatorial quantities linked to the language generated by the grammar, so it is possible to perform a thorough analysis of the reuse.

It is also useful to define a taxonomy of system architectures that can help in selecting the right protocol. For instance, it would appear that transputers are particularly well-suited for the request-subrequest protocol, as the cost of communication is low and there are strong limitations on storage; by contrast for parallel architecture based, say, on networks of workstations, local caching would appear as the most appropriate solution.

Our study of protocols for constraint-based communication is done within the Constraint-Based Knowledge Broker (CBKB) model, a recently introduced formalization of CCP where a sharp separation is drawn between the use of constraints for, respectively, local problem solving and communication. Compared to other formalization of CCP, the CBKB model allows more direct focus on communication issues, and hence on problem solving done via the interaction of cooperative agents.

Previous work on CBKB

In [1], the Constraint-Based Knowledge Broker model (CBKB) was introduced. First refinements of the request-subrequest protocol were given. These refinements dealt with reuse of information, recursion control, ordering of subrequest deliveries, and thresholds. In [2], a more precise definition for CBKB was given. A complexity analysis showed the advantages and disadvantages of the CBKB model in terms of number of messages, number of agents cloned, and number of generations through the broker-attached generators. An example was discussed in the context of chart parsing. In [3], the local caching protocol within CBKB was introduced and compared with the request-subrequest protocol. It became clear that most application should use both or even hybrid protocol schemes. Different examples, real values for the measure of reuse, and graphical examples of reuse potentials were illustrated. In order to address different execution environments (transputer, LAN-based workstation clusters, etc.), CBKB has been specified in two ways: First, in the declarative, rule-based language *LO* [4], and second, in a pseudo-imperative language using threads for the massively-parallel scheme [5]. In the latter paper, moreover, the notion of partial results was introduced. That is, not only the requests but also the results to a subproblem may be expressed using a set of constraints.

References

1. Andreoli, J.-M., Borghoff, U. M., Pareschi, R. (1994). Constraint-Based Knowledge Brokers. In: Hong, H. (ed.): *Proc. 1st Int. Symp. on Parallel Symbolic Computation (PASCOS '94)*, Hagenberg/Linz, Austria. Lecture Notes Series in Computing **5**, Singapore, New Jersey, London, Hong Kong: World Scientific, pp. 1–11.
2. Andreoli, J.-M., Borghoff, U. M., Pareschi, R. (1995). The Constraint-Based Knowledge Broker Model: Semantics, Implementation and Analysis. *J. Symbolic Computation*. submitted for publication.
3. Arcelli, F., Borghoff, U. M., Formato, F., Pareschi, R. (1995). Tuning Constraint-Based Communication in Distributed Problem Solving. submitted for publication.
4. Andreoli, J.-M., Pareschi, R. (1991). Communication as Fair Distribution of Knowledge. *Proc. Conf. on Object-Oriented Programming Systems, Languages and Applications (OOPSLA '91)*, Phoenix, AZ. ACM SIGPLAN Notices **26**:11, pp. 212–229.
5. Borghoff, U. M. (1995). An Imperative Specification of the Constraint-Based Knowledge Broker Model with Partial Results. Rank Xerox Research Centre, Grenoble Lab., France, Technical Report.